

Strongly-Typed Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming

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Abstract. This paper introduces Strongly-Typed Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming (ST-GSynGP), an extension of Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming (GSynGP), which is a tree-based Geometric GP variant that leverages geometric crossover in syntactic space to implicitly mitigate bloat and preserve locality. ST-GSynGP improves GSynGP’s applicability for complex problems by accommodating strongly typed and variable-arity functions directly into the geometric crossover mechanism. ST-GSynGP is compared to Strongly-typed Genetic Programming (STGP) across symbolic regression, Boolean logic, classification, and control benchmarks. Experimental results demonstrate that ST-GSynGP achieves competitive performance while consistently producing more compact and interpretable solutions. These findings demonstrate that combining strong typing with geometric syntactic recombination provides an effective foundation for evolving high-performing and interpretable machine learning models for a wide range of applications.

Keywords: Genetic Programming · Interpretability · Recombination operators

1 Introduction

Genetic Programming (GP) is a flexible evolutionary computation paradigm capable of producing intrinsically interpretable computer programs and Machine Learning models for target problems [5,16]. Despite its popularity, GP still faces several open problems. Those addressed in this study are bloat, generalisation to complex problems and the inefficient search space exploration.

Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming (GSynGP) [7,8] is a tree-based Geometric Genetic Programming (GGP) variant that has been shown to implicitly mitigate bloat. It does so by performing geometric recombinations of parent individuals in syntactic space, evolving compact and interpretable solutions that match the performance of traditional GP [5]. However, GSynGP, like most tree-based and geometric GP variants, does not handle symbols of multiple arities (non-terminal symbols with a variable number of arguments) and heterogeneous types, reducing its applicability to more complex problems.

Drawing inspiration from Strongly-typed Genetic Programming (STGP) [11], this study introduces ST-GSynGP, an extension of GSynGP that enhances its

generalisation capabilities for complex problems by accommodating variable arities and heterogeneous types through a strongly typed system (where symbols have explicitly defined data types).

Strong typing and geometric GP have remained largely separate research lines. Unifying them at the operator level is non-trivial, as heterogeneous types and variable arities alter the structure of the search space, change relationships between individuals, and may cause the geometric path between the parents to traverse invalid regions. ST-GSynGP addresses these issues, operating within valid typed regions and preserving the geometric properties of the syntactic crossover.

ST-GSynGP is compared to STGP in a set of benchmarks from the domains of symbolic regression, Boolean logic, classification, and control. The performance, size, and interpretability of the evolved solutions are analysed.

2 State of the Art

2.1 Bloat and Measuring Interpretability

One of GP’s main limitations is bloat, a phenomenon that translates to the uncontrolled growth of the solutions without corresponding performance improvements, which hinders interpretability and increases computational cost [18]. Several post-hoc measures to control bloat have been presented. Combining depth limiting with parsimony pressure to penalise large individuals generally outperforms other techniques, yet no single method dominates across all problem domains [6,19]. Other approaches include size-fair and homologous crossover that bias recombination towards equally sized parents, and multi-objective approaches where minimising model size is an explicit optimisation objective [16].

A particularly relevant feature of GP is the ability to produce intrinsically interpretable symbolic models [1]. However, bloat can ultimately undermine this advantage, as large and complex models often behave as black boxes. Quantifying interpretability is therefore crucial, typically addressed by assessing model complexity. Over the years, several metrics have been proposed, all of which partially assess models’ interpretability. However, measuring interpretability remains an open research problem characterised by significant subjectivity [1], but a common consensus holds that smaller models tend to be more interpretable. Accordingly, this study measures interpretability through a structural metric (tree size) and a functional metric (Proxies of Human Interpretability (PHI) [25]). PHI is computed as:

$$\phi(s, no, nao, naoc) = 79.2 - 0.2S - 0.5no - 3.4nao - 4.5naoc \quad (1)$$

where S is the tree size, n_o the number of operators, n_{ao} the number of non-arithmetic operators, and n_{aoc} the number of consecutive chains of non-arithmetic operations. The model was derived from hundreds of human assessments of symbolic model complexity. Higher values indicate greater perceived interpretability.

2.2 Geometric Genetic Programming Variants

Geometric variation operators interpret the search space as a metric space [14]. Geometric crossover generates offspring along a path linking the two parents, whereas geometric mutation generates individuals within a hypersphere centred on the original one [12]. Both allow for more controlled modifications by restricting the region of the search space being explored.

Geometric Semantic Genetic Programming (GSGP) [13] is a GGP approach that operates within the semantic space, representing individuals as output vectors and measuring distances through differences in output behaviour. Offspring result from linear combinations of parent functions, while mutation applies a linear combination of the individual with a random function. Although this approach presents a unimodal error surface, the recursive composition of individuals leads to severe bloat [22,9]. The Semantic Learning algorithm with Inflate and Deflate Mutations (SLIM_GSGP) [23,24] reduces this issue by introducing a deflate mutation that may subtract previously added terms, yielding smaller individuals, though at the cost of problem-specific hyperparameter tuning.

2.3 Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming

Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming (GSynGP) [7,8] performs geometric crossover in syntactic space rather than stochastic subtree swapping, as in standard GP. At the core of GSynGP lies its crossover operator, which iteratively transforms a copy of the first parent P_A towards the second parent P_B through incremental modifications guided by an edit distance that aligns their genomes, implicitly controlling the growth of the solutions and providing greater control over the magnitude of structural changes.

The parents' syntactic trees are mapped into strings via pre-order traversal, simplifying the gene alignment process by enabling the use of string edit algorithms rather than costly tree alignment.

The two prefix-notation strings are aligned using the Longest Common Subsequence (LCS) to identify the common and non-common genes between parent genotypes, creating two Modification Masks (M_A and M_B). As depicted in Figure 1, these masks include the common symbols (the LCS, shown in grey), annotated non-common genes with prefix F_ or T_ denoting membership of the function or terminal set, respectively, and blank spaces where genes must be inserted or removed to make a copy of the first parent more similar to the second.

At each iteration, one of four operations is applied: (1) deleting or (2) inserting a non-common function and a terminal, or (3 - 4) replacing a non-common function or terminal with another symbol of the respective type. Each iteration of GSynGP's crossover produces an offspring at a minimal distance from P_A . To explore the entire path between both parents, the operator is applied iteratively, where the result of iteration i serves as the starting point for iteration $i + 1$, until the maximum number of iterations is reached or P_B is reached. This approach controls the degree of transformation from P_A to P_B based on the number of iterations applied, ensuring a controlled exploration of the syntactic space. A

Fig. 1: Example of a GSynGP crossover operation

notable feature of this mechanism is its ability to implicitly control bloat. When all four operations are available, each iteration has only a 25% chance of growing the offspring, with any growth limited to a maximum of two nodes (the arity of the functions used).

For example, consider the two individuals and their corresponding modification masks depicted in Figure 1, with binary functions $\{\text{IfFoodAhead}, \text{Progn2}\}$, terminals $\{\text{move}, \text{left}, \text{right}\}$ and the LCS $\{\text{Progn2}, \text{move}\}$. Applying delete, it removes $F_IfFoodAhead$ and T_move from P_A , obtaining the offspring O . Decoding yields tree $\text{Progn2}(\text{left}, \text{move})$, one step away from P_A towards P_B .

2.4 Strongly-Typed Genetic Programming

Standard GP relies on the property of closure, which states that all functions and terminals within a building model must be compatible with one another [5]. This assumption allows broad combinations but restricts GP to single-type domains, rendering it unsuitable for problems that require mixed data types. Strongly typed programming languages require the explicit specification of the type of each data structure, variable, and function, enabling code to treat different data types appropriately, detect type-related errors, and prevent invalid or conflicting operations.

This is the basis of Strongly Typed Genetic Programming (STGP) [11], which is a variant of GP that enforces a strict, strongly typed data system, ensuring that all generated solutions adhere to predefined type constraints. Solutions are represented as type-constrained syntactic trees, with nodes associated with explicitly defined input/output data types. Such constraints enable generalisation to more complex problems involving multiple data types [11,17].

The Strongly Typed Function Definitions (Table 1) are central structures that indicate the types of each function or terminal. They prevent invalid individuals and allow classic genetic operators to work in a strongly typed environment [11,17]. In STGP, the genetic operators function similarly to those in standard GP. However, candidate operations are filtered through the Strongly Typed Function Definitions, ensuring valid offspring.

Table 1: Examples of Strongly Typed Function Definitions [11]

Function Name	Arguments	Return Type
DOT-PRODUCT-3	VECTOR-3, VECTOR-3	FLOAT
VECTOR-ADD-2	VECTOR-2, VECTOR-2	VECTOR-2
MAT-VEC-MULT-4-3	MATRIX-4-3, VECTOR-3	VECTOR-4
CAR-FLOAT	LIST-OF-FLOAT	FLOAT
LENGHT-VECTOR-4	LIST-OF-VECTOR-4	INTEGER
IF-THEN-ELSE-INT	BOOLEAN, INTEGER, INTEGER	INTEGER

3 Strongly-typed Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming (ST-GSynGP)

This section introduces ST-GSynGP, a novel extension of GSynGP based on the principles of STGP, to overcome the limitations in handling variable arities and heterogeneous data types. To do so, the following modifications are made to the building model and the crossover operator.

3.1 Building Model

Function	Arity	Arg types	Return
if-then-else	3	bool float float	float
add	2	float float	float
sub	2	float float	float
mult	2	float float	float
div	2	float float	float
and	2	bool bool	bool
or	2	bool bool	bool
lt	2	float float	bool
eq	2	float float	bool
not	1	bool	bool

Table 2: Function Types Table (Spambase)

Symbol	Type
bool	bool
var_1, \dots, var_n	float
ephemeral constant	float

Table 3: Terminal Types Table (Spambase)

The building model consists of sets of symbols and rules that define the search space in ST-GSynGP. Besides the Function Set and the Terminal Set, the following novel structures are introduced: the *Type Set*, comprising the collection of all data types; the *Function Types Table*, which explicitly maps the type set to the function set, specifying for each function symbol its arity (number of arguments), return type, and the type of each argument (Table 2); and the *Terminal Types Table*, which maps the Type Set to the Terminal Set, explicitly defining the type of each terminal (Table 3).

ST-GSynGP introduces a strongly typed system in which every symbol has an explicitly defined data type and a fixed arity. A syntactic tree is valid if

and only if, at every node, the return type of each child matches the expected argument type of its parent function. Variable arities are accommodated by allowing functions with different arities to coexist in the same function set, each fully specified in the Function Types Table. All components of the evolutionary process consult these tables to ensure that every generated individual remains type and arity-consistent throughout evolution.

3.2 Crossover operator

To devise ST-GSynGP, the existing operations in GSynGP are adapted to accommodate variable arities and heterogeneous data types, as follows:

- *deleteFT_mat*: Simultaneous removal of a non-common function and as many non-common terminal arguments of corresponding data types as its *arity* – 1, from P_A ;
- *insertFT_mat*: Simultaneous insertion of a function and as many terminal arguments of corresponding data types as its *arity* – 1, from P_B into P_A ;
- *replaceT_mat*: Replacement of a terminal in P_A by another terminal of the same data type from P_B ;
- *replaceF_mat*: Replacement of a function in P_A by another function with the same arity, data types of arguments, and return data type from P_B .

In GSynGP, the *deleteFT* removes a function and a terminal symbol. This is intended to maintain the proportion of functions and terminals, ensuring the validity of the offspring. As an example, consider the individual +ab. If you remove a function (+) and a terminal (b) from it, you would still get a valid individual, with a single terminal symbol (a). To accommodate varying arities, this rule must be generalised to remove a function and as many terminals as its *arity* – 1.

The operation *deleteFT_mat* starts by attempting to remove a random non-common function from P_A . Upon removal, the function’s arity and the data type of each argument are retrieved from the Function Types Table. Subsequently, the operator attempts to remove k randomly chosen non-common terminals from P_A , where k equals the function’s *arity* – 1. The retained terminal replaces the sub-tree composed of the function and its arguments, maintaining the validity of the individual.

For example, consider the two individuals and their corresponding modification masks depicted in Figure 2, following the building model presented on Tables 2 and 3. Applying *deleteFT_mat*, F_eq and T_var_6 may be removed from P_A , obtaining the offspring O.

Analogously, the operation *insertFT_mat* attempts to insert a random non-common function from P_B into a corresponding empty index within P_A . Once a candidate function is inserted, its arity and argument data types are retrieved. The operator then seeks to fill as many empty positions in P_A as the function’s *arity* – 1, using random non-common terminals from P_B whose corresponding indices in P_A are also empty. This insertion is subject to the conditions that the

Fig. 2: Example of the *deleteFT_mat* operation

data types of the inserted terminals match the corresponding function arguments, and that the insertion indices in P_A follow the function's index.

The *replaceF_mat* and *replaceT_mat* operations are performed according to three different scenarios, depending on the content of the modification masks. Regardless of the scenario, the procedure begins by randomly selecting a non-common function/terminal from P_B .

- If the corresponding position in P_A is empty, a random non-common compatible function/terminal from P_A is removed, and the symbol from P_B is placed in the empty position of P_A .
- If the corresponding position in P_A contains a non-common compatible function/terminal, a direct replacement is performed.
- If the corresponding position in P_A neither contains a non-common function/terminal nor is empty, another random non-common compatible function/terminal from P_A is selected, and a direct replacement occurs.

For *replaceT_mat*, compatibility requires matching data types. For *replaceF_mat*, compatibility requires matching arity and argument data types, and return data type. In all scenarios, if arity and type conditions are not met, the operations are attempted again with another randomly selected non-common symbol of P_B .

3.3 Validity of individuals

As mentioned in the Section 1, heterogeneous types and variable arities alter the structure of the search space, change relationships between individuals, and may cause the geometric path between parents to traverse invalid regions. In this section, some mechanisms to mitigate invalid individuals are proposed.

In the *deleteFT_mat* and *insertFT_mat* operations, the relative position of the removed or inserted function and its associated terminals is critical. To illustrate this, consider applying the *insertFT_mat* operation using the building model detailed on Tables 2 and 3. Further consider two individuals for the Spambase problem and their corresponding modification masks, shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Examples of the generation of partially mapped individuals. The coloured genes in O_2 and O_3 are not mapped to the phenotype

Consider the goal of inserting the *if-then-else* function along with the terminals `var_6` and `var_3` from P_B into P_A , varying only the insertion position, and yielding offspring O_1 and O_2 . Based on the building model, the first offspring adheres to type and arity restrictions and is fully valid. The second offspring, however, presents the *if-then-else* symbol with only two arguments, as one of the involved terminals was inserted before the function; consequently, only the `T_var_6` symbol is mapped to the phenotype since the remaining genes don't adhere to arity restrictions, resulting in a partially mapped individual. To minimise these situations, it was established that the terminals involved in insertion or deletion operations must be located downstream from the involved functions, preventing the operation that originated O_2 .

Despite the precedence rule described above significantly reducing the number of invalid or partially mapped individuals, it does not entirely prevent them. To address this, a validation mechanism is employed wherein the genotype is mapped to the phenotype and then back to the genotype. If the original and remapped genotypes match, the individual is fully valid, and the operation returns the descendant as the result of the crossover. If this condition is not satisfied, a partially mapped individual is returned, the genotype is truncated, and the modification masks are corrected. If the validation mechanism cannot map any part of the individual, the individual will be considered to be invalid, and the original individuals will be recovered in their entirety.

To clarify the concept of partially mapped individuals, consider the third offspring (O_3) presented in Figure 3, generated by inserting the `eq` function alongside the terminal `var_6` from P_B into P_A . Even though the previously described precedence rule is followed, the offspring is not fully mapped, as function `eq` does not have enough parameters, and so only the symbol `bool` is mapped to the phenotype. To increase diversity and minimise the propagation of this effect, rather than discarding such individuals entirely, ST-GSynGP accepts

Table 4: Parameters

Parameter	Value
Population size	250
Generations	500
Crossover probability	0.7
Mutation probability	0.3
Elite size	3
Tournament size	2
Maximum depth of initial trees	6
Maximum tree depth	17
Number of independent trials	30

them as partially mapped individuals, truncates their genotype to the longest valid prefix and the modification masks are corrected accordingly.

4 Experimental Setup

The evolutionary process follows the classic GP life-cycle [5]. Population initialisation uses a type and arity-constrained variant of Ramped Half-and-Half in which when generating an internal node, the selection of the function symbol is performed randomly from the filtered function set with the appropriate return type, generating as many sub-trees as the function arity indicates. When generating a leaf node, the selection of the terminal symbol is chosen randomly from the filtered terminal set matching the required type [16,11]. Mate selection uses an adaptation of Clearing Tournament Selection [15] in which niches are composed of individuals with identical genotypes. A type-compatible node mutation is applied [11]. Elitist selection determines survivors, and the termination criterion is the number of generations.

ST-GSynGP is compared to Montana’s STGP [11] on a set of problems from the domains of symbolic regression, boolean function synthesis, classification and reinforcement learning/control [10]. The Vladislavleva-7 and N-Multiplexers problems were selected because they are well-established, facilitating performance comparisons and only need a single data type, allowing the isolated evaluation of variable-arity handling. Spambase and Lunar Lander introduce mixed data types, assessing the full typed generalisation capabilities of ST-GSynGP.

Datasets were split 80%/20% for training and testing. In Lunar Lander, the trained models were tested in random environments. The main metrics to be studied will be fitness and individual interpretability. Except for the crossover operator, the implementation of STGP is analogous to that of ST-GSynGP, as presented above. As a result, they share most of the parameters, as indicated on Table 4. ST-GSynGP has an additional parameter to control the number of crossover iterations. In this work, the crossover operator is applied for a number

of iterations sampled uniformly at random, generating offspring in-between both parents.¹

Statistical comparisons use 30 independent trials per algorithm with identical initial conditions. Normality was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test and variance homogeneity with Levene’s test; the paired t -test is applied when both assumptions hold, and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test otherwise.

4.1 Evaluation Problems

Symbolic Regression Problem serves as a fundamental benchmark in GP, assessing an algorithm’s capacity to approximate mathematical expressions and navigate continuous search space. **Vladislavleva-7** involves a single data type and functions of variable arity, making it suitable for evaluating arity handling independently of type heterogeneity. **Vladislavleva7** [10]: Expressed as:

$$f(x, y) = (x - 3)(y - 3) + 2 \sin((x - 4)(y - 4)) \quad (2)$$

This problem involves two variables and non-linear relationships. Following the specification of [10], the training set comprises 300 points sampled uniformly from $[0.05, 6.05]^2$ and the test set comprises 1000 points sampled uniformly from $[-0.25, 6.35]^2$. Fitness is assessed by the Mean Squared Error (MSE) [3]. The function and terminal domains are as in [10], and presented on Tables 7 and 8 of the Supplementary Material [20].

N-Multiplexer Problems necessitate the evolution of multiplexer circuits capable of correctly selecting data inputs based on address bit values [4]. The output corresponds to the data bit specified by the binary value formed by the address bits. **N-Multiplexer6**: Comprises 2 address bits (a_0, a_1) and 4 data bits (d_0-d_3), yielding 6 inputs. **N-Multiplexer11**: An extended version featuring 3 address bits (a_0-a_2) and 8 data bits (d_0-d_7), totalling 11 inputs. The fitness of individuals is calculated by the percentage of incorrect results in all 2^N possible combinations of inputs ($N = 6$ or $N = 11$), resulting in a minimisation problem. Fitness is therefore given by: Fitness = Total possible cases – Correct cases. To solve these problems, both algorithms use the same function and terminal domains as in [4], presented on Tables 9 and 10 in the Supplementary Material [20].

Spambase Problem [2] is a classification task designed to evaluate Machine Learning (ML) in the context of email spam detection. It involves predicting whether an email is spam or non-spam based on 57 predictive attributes. This problem is particularly relevant for assessing GP performance in real-world classification challenges and handling mixed data types. The dataset consists of 4601 instances, each with 57 features and a binary target (0 for non-spam, 1 for spam). Fitness evaluation is conducted using the F1 score [3]. Considering the remaining problems, the fitness evaluation is transformed into a minimisation problem, for better readability, as follows: $F1_minimisation = 100.0 - (F1_score * 100.0)$ To solve these problems, both algorithms use the same sets of terminals and functions, presented on Tables 2 and 3.

¹ The code for these experiments is available on the following repository: Code

Lunar Lander Problem [21] is a reinforcement learning/agent control task where the objective is to generate a controller to safely land a spacecraft on a designated pad on a simulated lunar surface. This problem is particularly relevant for assessing GP capability in handling discrete action spaces in dynamic and complex environments. The environment provides an eight-dimensional state space comprising the x and y coordinates, the corresponding velocities, the landers orientation angle, its angular velocity, and two Boolean leg-contact indicators. The action space is discrete and consists of four possible actions: 0 (no action), 1 (activate the left engine), 2 (activate the main engine), and 3 (activate the right engine). In this setup, the environment is configured with wind enabled (wind power = 15.0) and turbulence (turbulence power = 1.5), introducing stochastic elements to the landing task.

The fitness evaluation is conducted by executing the evolved controller in the Lunar Lander environment for five episodes, each with a maximum of 1000 steps, as presented in [21]. At each step, the evolved controller generates an action based on the current state of the environment. The total reward for each episode is obtained by adding the reward values assigned at each step. The individual’s final fitness score is defined as the negative average cumulative reward over these episodes, transforming the problem into a minimisation task. The fitness function follows the implementation suggested in [21]. Since both the observation space and the action space are included in the terminal set, the evolved controller may return observation symbols as output, which are not valid actions. To discourage this, a penalty of 6 points is applied to the fitness score each time an invalid action is returned. This value was empirically determined to be the minimum sufficient to significantly reduce such occurrences. To address this problem, the function and terminal domains used are presented on Tables 11 and 12 in the Supplementary Material [20]².

5 Experimental Results

This section analyses the performance of ST-GSynGP in comparison with STGP across multiple problem domains. The evaluation assesses solution quality, generalisation performance, and interpretability, supported by statistical significance testing.

5.1 Fitness of the Evolved Solutions

The goal of these algorithms is to find solutions to a problem. As such, in this section, we shall compare them based on the performance of the best evolved solutions. Figure 4 and Figure 5 depict the boxplots of the fitness, in both train and test, of the best solutions outputted by the two algorithms, over 30 independent trials, while Table 5 presents the results of the pairwise statistical hypothesis tests applied to the same data. As can be seen, ST-GSynGP

² Supplementary Material available at: Supplementary Material

significantly outperforms STGP in Lunar Lander, hinting that its controllers are better suited to cope with complex control problems in dynamic and stochastic environments. The two algorithms perform equivalently on both NMultipler problems, while STGP outperforms ST-GSynGP in Spambase and Vladislavleva7, indicating that STGP retains an advantage in problems that seem to require larger program structures. Overall, these results demonstrate that ST-GSynGP is competitive with STGP in terms of fitness, being a particularly interesting choice in scenarios where compact representations are advantageous.

Fig. 4: Best Individual Fitness in Train (Minimisation) Fig. 5: Best Individual Fitness in Test (Minimisation)

Table 5: P-values - Best Individual Fitness. ^WWilcoxon; ^TT-Test.

Metric	Spambase	Lunar Lander	NMultipler6	NMultipler11	Vladislavleva7
Train	0.0000 ^W	0.0000 ^W	0.3203 ^T	0.7000 ^W	0.0000 ^W
Test	0.0000 ^W	0.0000 ^W	0.1663 ^W	0.2321 ^T	0.0005 ^W

5.2 Interpretability of the Evolved Solutions

Interpretability analysis reveals a consistent advantage for ST-GSynGP. Best individual tree sizes are significantly smaller for ST-GSynGP in most benchmarks,

with equivalent performance only in the N-Multiplexer tasks. This confirms that the implicit bloat control characteristic of geometric syntactic operators remains effective under strong typing and variable arity constraints (see Table 6 and Figure 6). Furthermore, PHI consistently favours ST-GSynGP across most problems (see Table 6 and Figure 7). The only exception is NMultiplexer problems, where the two approaches yield similar interpretability; this is because both algorithms find optimal, identical solutions very quickly. These results demonstrate that ST-GSynGP produces models that are not only smaller but also structurally simpler and more readable, reinforcing its suitability for applications where transparency is essential.

Fig. 6: Best Individual Tree Size (Minimisation)

Fig. 7: PHI (Maximization)

Table 6: P-values - Wilcoxon Test - Interpretability

Metric	Spambase	Lunar Lander	NMultiplexer6	NMultiplexer11	Vladislavleva7
Tree Size	0.0	0.0	0.0935	0.6405	0.0
PHI	0.0	0.0	0.0716	0.8465	0.0

One of the best individuals evolved by ST-GSynGP for Spambase is $(capital_run_length_longest \geq 9.4) \wedge (word_freq_650 == 0.0)$ in which True

corresponds to the spam class. As can be seen, the obtained model is interpretable, exhibiting a concise structure and clear decision logic. In turn, the corresponding individual from STGP had 318 nodes, making it impossible to be interpreted.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper proposes ST-GSynGP, an extension of GSynGP that enables geometric syntactic variation in the presence of heterogeneous data types and variable-arity operators. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to integrate strong typing and variable arity directly into a geometric syntactic crossover while preserving locality, implicit bloat control, and individual validity.

The core contribution of this work is to embed explicit type and arity constraints into the geometric crossover operator itself, rather than treating typing as an external filter. ST-GSynGP preserves the geometric interpretation of syntactic variation while restricting the search to valid regions of the space. This distinguishes it from STGP, which relies on subtree-based operators that may induce disruptive structural changes and uncontrolled growth.

Experimental results across symbolic regression, Boolean function synthesis, classification, and reinforcement learning benchmarks demonstrate that ST-GSynGP consistently produces significantly more compact and interpretable programs than STGP, confirming that the implicit bloat control characteristic of geometric syntactic operators remains effective under strong typing and variable arity constraints.

ST-GSynGP is competitive with STGP in terms of solution quality and generalisation, matching its performance across several benchmarks and outperforming it in a stochastic control task (Lunar Lander). The results do not suggest that ST-GSynGP universally dominates STGP in raw fitness. Instead, they highlight a consistent trade-off between expressive capacity and solution compactness. Overall, ST-GSynGP is particularly well-suited for domains where interpretability, robustness, and generalisation are prioritised over marginal gains in training fitness.

These findings reinforce an important message, search operators matter as much as representations. Showing that enforcing geometric locality and syntactic constraints at the operator level provides a viable alternative to explicit bloat penalties or post-hoc simplification, particularly when interpretability is a primary concern.

This work opens several avenues for future research. First, the present study focused exclusively on crossover, extending ST-GSynGP with geometric, type-aware mutation operators would allow a more complete assessment of typed geometric search dynamics. Second, another promising direction concerns the handling of partially interpretable individuals. Rather than treating partial interpretation as a validation failure, future work could explore graded validity measures or repair-based mechanisms, potentially exploiting intermediate structures as useful stepping stones in the search space. Finally, while this work relied on established PHI, future studies should be complemented with more interpretability metrics.

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